

DEVELOPMENT OF WELLNESS TOURISM UNDER SUSTAINABILITY (IN CASE OF VALENCIA, SPAIN)

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Abstract. *The article analyses sustainability factors in tourism and describes how they open up a wide range of opportunities for improvement of wellness tourism. The presented measures to ensure sustainability are outlined using examples from developed countries; in particular, Spain, and conclusions and proposals are made for the sustainable development of wellness tourism in Uzbekistan in the future.*

Key words: *Sustainability, depletion of natural resources, wellness, wellness tourism, health tourism, medical tourism, beach tourism.*

Just as any industry has an impact on the environment, the development of the tourism sector also causes a number of negative comments. The negative effects of tourism occur when visitors overuse natural resources. Uncontrolled traditional tourism poses a potential threat to many natural areas around the world. It puts enormous pressure on these areas and leads to soil erosion, increased pollution, waste dumping into the sea (beach tourism), loss of natural habitat (construction of tourist resorts), increased pressure on endangered species (hunting tourism), etc. The occurrence of negative consequences, such as an increase in forest fires, causes enormous harm to human life.

The negative impacts of tourism on nature can be divided into 3 groups:

Depletion of natural resources. Water, and especially fresh water, is one of the most important natural resources. The tourism industry usually overuses water resources for hotels, swimming pools, golf courses and personal needs of tourists. This can lead to water shortages and deterioration of water supply, as well as an increase in wastewater. Tourism can put significant pressure on local resources such as energy, food and other raw materials that may already be in short supply. Increased extraction and transportation of these resources will increase the physical impacts associated with their use; Important land resources include minerals, fossil fuels, fertile soil, forests, wetlands and wildlife. The growth of tourism and the development of recreational activities have increased the pressure on these resources and scenic landscapes. Direct impacts on renewable and non-renewable natural resources in the provision of tourism facilities can arise from the use of land and building materials for accommodation and other infrastructure.

Pollution - any type of transport used during travel, eg. Transport emissions and waste from energy production and use are linked to acid rain, global warming and photochemical pollution. Air pollution from tourist transport is a global problem, particularly due to carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions associated with the energy use of transport and the disposal of waste by tourists at various locations.

Physical impacts – destruction of wetlands, parks, cultural heritage sites and other similar objects by tourists. These negative consequences affect not only the environment but also human

health. Climate change, the negative impact of humanity and technology on nature also seriously affect human health.

For that reason, sustainable tourism has been promoted as a form of tourism development in the 21st century in the official program of the United Nations – Agenda 21. Chapter 4 of Agenda 21 is entitled “Protecting and managing the natural resource base of economic and social development” and its Article 43 states: “Promote sustainable tourism development, including non-consumptive and eco-tourism, ... in order to increase the benefits from tourism resources for the population in host communities while maintaining the cultural and environmental integrity of the host communities and enhancing the protection of ecologically sensitive areas and natural heritages; promote sustainable tourism development and capacity building in order to contribute to the strengthening of rural and local communities”

Serbian scientists Marija Kostic and Melita Jovanovic-Tončev stated in their scientific work on the importance of sustainable tourism, that, sustainable tourism provides a balance between economic development and the constraints imposed by the environment and the needs of local populations.

The concept of sustainable development gained recognition with the introduction of the World Conservation Strategy (WCS) in 1980 and gained further prominence through the Brundtland Report in 1987. The report defined sustainable development as meeting the present's needs without jeopardizing future generations' ability to meet theirs. This definition underscores the importance of integrating economic, social, and environmental considerations into decision-making for long-term stability (Reid, 2007). Sustainable development encompasses three interconnected dimensions:

Economic sustainability: Focuses on creating local employment, generating income, and improving quality of life.

Social sustainability: Emphasizes equitable distribution of benefits and preservation of cultural values.

Environmental sustainability: Aims to conserve biodiversity and promote the sustainable use of natural resources (Asara et al., 2015).

These principles are mirrored in the sustainable tourism framework outlined by UNEP and UNWTO (2005), which prioritizes environmental conservation, cultural authenticity, and economically sustainable practices that benefit all stakeholders.

Sustainable tourism is pivotal in enhancing tourism's positive impact on biodiversity conservation while addressing poverty reduction and environmental protection. It advocates reinvesting tourism revenues into conservation projects and empowering local communities through capacity-building programs to effectively manage protected areas (Matharu & Xalxo, 2017). Nonetheless, achieving a balance between economic growth and environmental preservation poses challenges, as many destinations face difficulties in implementing sustainable practices within their operations (Harrison, 2015).

The Countries around the world have developed different strategies to develop sustainable tourism in their regions. Many destinations in the European and American continents are leading the way in terms of sustainability. According to Euro monitor International, 41% of travelers said they would pay 30% more for adventure and ecotourism, with the city having the highest sustainability rating among 112 cities in Europe and the Americas by the end of 2022. It formed a list of ten.

Table 1. List of the 10 most sustainable cities.

Cities	Ranks (2022)	Ranks (2021)	Differences (2021-2022)
Melbourne (Australia)	1	0	Not on the list in 2021
Madrid (Spain)	2	2	Retained its place
Seville (Spain)	3	6	+3
Stockholm (Scotland)	4	1	-3
Tallinn (Estonia)	5	2	-3
Toronto (Canada)	6	16	+10
Palma de Mallorca (Spain)	7	11	+4
Las Vegas (USA)	8	2	-6
Lisbon (Portugal)	9	4	-5
Munich (Germany)	10	8	-2

Although Melbourne tops the table, three cities in Spain deserve attention. We see that Madrid (2nd place), Seville (3rd place) and Palma de Mallorca (7th place) are in the top ten.

Below, we analyze the Spanish government’s organizational and strategic priorities for sustainable development.

In 2005, the Spanish government pledged to promote the UNWTO Global Code of Ethics for Tourism within the country’s tourism industry. Over the past two decades, this code has evolved into a guiding vision for the future of Spain’s tourism sector. Additionally, the government has demonstrated its commitment to sustainability by investing significantly in the Competitiveness and Modernization Plan, allocating an unprecedented \$3.8 billion (€3.4 billion) to enhance tourism destinations and businesses nationwide. This includes \$110 million (€100 million) from NextGenerationEU recovery funds dedicated to the Spain Tourism Experience Program, which focuses on improving tourism quality and visitor experiences.

In 2023, Spain launched its third call for sustainable tourism plans, approving 175 initiatives to foster sustainability throughout the country. \$527 million (€478 million) back these projects from NextGenerationEU funds.

In 2016, Spain implemented Law 2/2016, passed on March 30, introducing a tax on tourist stays in the Balearic Islands to fund sustainable tourism measures (LIET). The law established a tax aimed at generating revenue for environmental protection and sustainable tourism initiatives both within and beyond the islands. It also created a fund to support sustainable tourism projects and formed the Commission for the Promotion of Sustainable Tourism, tasked with developing annual plans to prioritize goals with an emphasis on territorial balance. Decree 35/2016, enacted on June 23, further detailed the tax and its measures to support sustainable tourism.

Since the law’s implementation, visitors to Mallorca, Menorca, Ibiza, and Formentera have contributed to sustainable tourism through the Sustainable Tourism Tax, which has funded essential projects to protect the environment, preserve cultural heritage, and promote sustainable practices. In 2023, the tax generated €133,342,900 in revenue.

The tourism board has outlined several key upcoming projects, including:

A new railway link between Manacor and Artà, Mallorca: This project will bring modern rail infrastructure to eastern Mallorca, offering an alternative transport option along this popular route.

New walking and cycling routes in Ibiza and Mallorca: Repurposing old railway tracks, these “greenway paths” aim to blend heritage restoration with sustainable transportation for cyclists and walkers.

A pedestrianized path between Santa Maria and Inca, Mallorca: A 2.7-kilometer stretch of the MA-13A road will be redesigned for pedestrians, connecting Santa Maria and Inca while passing through Consell and Binissalem, with additional improvements to the roadway.

Supporting sustainable development in human life has led to the emergence of wellness tourism. Traveling in a healthy environment helps restore health. Spain also supports a strategy to create a healthy environment through revenues from a sustainable tourism tax to promote health tourism.

In October 2024, Spain welcomed 9.0 million foreign tourists, up 9.5% from the same month in 2023. In the first 10 months of 2024, the number of tourists grew by 10.8%.

Spain is one of the strongest wellness tourism markets in Europe. With its climate, sunny beaches along the Mediterranean, lush green landscapes in the north and majestic mountain ranges, the country is not only tranquil, but also offers many opportunities for active recreation. From swimming and beach yoga to hiking and nature walks, any activity is ideal for a wellness program. In addition, there are more than 100 sanatoriums with therapeutic mineral water, 10 thousand clinical studies, which is a major incentive for the development of wellness tourism in the country.

In the country, wellness tourism is considered a subcategory of health tourism and is described as follows.

Figure 2. Classification of health tourism in Spain

Thus, in Spain, health tourism is a combination of curative and preventive tourism, and wellness services include all the processes that prevent diseases: spa, massage, meditation, yoga, sports activities (running, cycling). This includes things like walking, healthy eating and physiotherapy (hot springs, aromatherapy, hot sand, salt, etc.). Environmental sustainability plays a very important role in wellness tourism, since a healthy environment provides humanity with a healthy spirit and physical stamina.

Wellness travel is a form of tourism that emphasizes improving physical, mental, and emotional health while discovering new destinations. It appeals to environmentally conscious travelers who value sustainable practices. Many hotels and resorts are actively contributing to environmental preservation by adopting eco-friendly measures like utilizing renewable energy, minimizing waste, and offering locally sourced organic cuisine. These initiatives ensure wellness travel revitalizes individuals while promoting environmental sustainability.

Spain, a leader in sustainable development, was named European Green Capital by the European Commission in 2024. Valencia, situated on Spain's southeastern coast, is home to 837,000 residents and serves as the capital of the province sharing its name. The city was awarded the European Green Capital 2024 title in recognition of its accomplishments in sustainable tourism, climate neutrality, and its commitment to a fair and inclusive green transition.

An impressive 97% of Valencia's population lives within 300 meters of green urban spaces. The city has demonstrated a strong dedication to enhancing air quality and restoring natural ecosystems, including the Devesa dune and wetland habitats. Additionally, Valencia promotes sustainable, healthy, and inclusive food systems through its innovative "Neighbourhood and Food Programme".

The city of Valencia, suitable for health tourism, is illustrated by the following infographic “Why tourists choose Valencia?” Briefly and fully describes the city’s capabilities. In particular, the infrastructure for wellness tourism:

- More than 160 km of cycling and walking paths throughout the city;
- Recreation areas along the coast;
- Sustainable transport, including:

RENFE

As Spain's national railway operator, Renfe is intrinsically focused on sustainability. In 2023, it transported a record 522 million passengers, effectively removing 350 million private vehicles from the roads. Despite its trains already being 90% electric and powered entirely by renewable energy with zero emissions, Renfe is investing over \$6 million (€5.5 million) to further enhance energy efficiency and fleet accessibility. Additionally, the company is piloting a \$29 million (€27 million) photovoltaic energy plant in Olmedo, the first of 37 planned across the country. This facility will improve train traction efficiency and enable Renfe to sell excess energy to the market.

IBERIA

As Spain's flagship airline, Iberia is dedicated to reducing emissions by modernizing its fleet, optimizing operations, and increasing the use of sustainable aviation fuels. Its sustainability efforts also focus on minimizing onboard waste and enhancing the social impact of its initiatives, such as assessing the economic benefits of Iberia’s routes and improving accessibility for travelers with disabilities.

Figure 3. “Why do tourists choose Valencia?”

Considering the natural potential of the city, it is worth noting that there are 300 sunny days a year and 5 million square meters of green space for various events. The created

opportunities are widely used not only by tourists, but also by residents of the city. The city of Valencia intends to implement the following steps to further develop health tourism.

- Identification and management of wellness-related services;
- Complementarity with medical tourism;
- Improvement of the autonomous community legal framework for thermalism;
- Wellness tourism advertising campaign;
- Collaboration agreement with the regional ministry of health;
- Promotion in primary care centers;
- Nominative line with the Valencian association of thermal resorts;
- Training and awareness;
- Promotional material;
- Plan for health tourism fairs and events;
- Brand creation and positioning.

As a result of my research conducted in Spain, theoretical provisions were formed that ensure the gradual sustainable development of wellness tourism in our country. It is expected that if this strategy is implemented, both sustainable and wellness tourism will develop simultaneously in Uzbekistan.

At the initial stage, the wellness tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan will be adapted to sustainable development in three main categories of sustainability: environmental (nature protection), social and economic.

Secondly, the next stage is to conduct regular marketing activities to attract tourists; In this regard, it is important to have websites to attract online tourists to each resort, as well as to develop a symbol of sustainable development at the resorts. This stage, of course, also includes the use of innovative smart technologies and the creation of digital platforms for managing sustainable tourism.

The final stage is to monitor the implementation of these tasks and assess their level in improving the quality of service.

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